

STUDIES IN FRIEDEL-CRAFTS REACTION. PART I. CONDENSATION OF ANISOLE WITH AN $\alpha\beta$ -UNSATURATED KETONE

BY HARINARAYAN KHASTAGIR AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

The Friedel-Craft reaction between anisole and ethyl-2-methyl-cyclohex-5-en-1-one-2-carboxylate furnishes ethyl-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-6-methylcyclohexanone-6-carboxylate which on hydrolysis, followed by reduction of the keto group, dehydration and sulphur dehydrogenation, yields 4'-methoxy-4-methyl-biphenyl.

Cook and Hewett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1098) have made attempts to cyclise phenyl-acetylcyclohexene, using aluminium chloride under mild conditions, but without any success. Recently however, Gutsche and Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2239) have re-investigated the work and by carrying out the reaction under more drastic conditions than those described by Cook and Hewett (*loc. cit.*) have been successful in effecting cyclisation, although in low yield, and identified the cyclised product as 9-keto-4b : 5 : 6 : 7 : 8 : 8a : 9 : 10-octahydrophenanthrene. Ghosh (*Science & Culture*, 1937, 13, 55) obtained 2-phenylcyclohexane-acetic acid in presence of aluminium chloride, while Cook and Goulden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1559) and Nenitzescu and Gavat (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1883) definitely isolated only 4-phenylcyclohexane-acetic acid from the same reaction. Gutsche and Johnson (*loc. cit.*) from their findings suggest that the reaction product consists of a mixture of position as well as stereoisomers, the conditions of experiment determine the main product. With a view to synthesising certain phenanthrene derivatives which will serve as intermediates for the synthesis of Oestrone, the Friedel-Crafts reaction between anisole and the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone, methyl-2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxycyclohex-6-ene-acetate (*Science & Culture*, 1947, 12, 410) was carried out, but considerable difficulties were experienced in determining the true course of the reaction, the latter compound being a $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated ester as well. In view of the above facts we have carried out the reaction with a simpler system and have described the results in the present communication.

Ethyl-2-methylcyclohex-5-en-1-one-2-carboxylate (Mukherjee, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 155) was condensed with anisole at low temperature, in presence of aluminium chloride and dry HCl gas to yield (I), which on hydrolysis by aqueous alkali furnished the ketone (II). The ketone was converted into oxime when only one product having m.p. 173° was isolated, showing the absence of isomers by the migration of anisyl residue under the conditions of the experiment. The ketone was reduced to the secondary alcohol by sodium and alcohol or with sodium and moist ether and dehydrated with anhydrous potassium hydrogen sulphate. The dehydration product, thus obtained, was dehydrogenated with sulphur to yield 4-methyl-4'-methoxybiphenyl (III). The three isomeric methoxymethyl-biphenyls were prepared from the Grignard complex obtained from *p*-bromoanisole and *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-methylcyclohexanones. The authentic sample of 4-methyl-4'-methoxy-biphenyl (m.p. 110°) showed no depression when mixed

solution was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and distilled. The residual oil was distilled, b.p. $165^\circ\text{--}170^\circ/4$ mm., yield 4.2 g. (Found: C, 76.41; H, 8.15. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.06; H, 8.25 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared by refluxing the ketone (1 g.) with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (1 g.), pyridine (1.5 c.c.), absolute alcohol (3 c.c.) for 5 hours. On dilution with water a solid contaminated with oil separated out; the alcohol was then boiled off and the solid was filtered. The residue on the filter paper was crystallised several times from rectified spirit, m.p. 173° . (Found: C, 72.45; H, 7.7; N, 5.98. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 72.10; H, 8.15; N, 6.00 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was also prepared by the alcohol-pyridine method. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. $185\text{--}86^\circ$ with previous shrinking at 183° .

4'-Methoxy-4-methyl-biphenyl (III).—(a). The ketone (II, 3.2 g.) was reduced with Na (4.5 g.) and absolute alcohol (90 c.c.). The sodium was added in thin slices from the top of the condenser. When all the sodium was dissolved it was cooled and diluted with iced-water and then extracted with ether. The ether-layer was washed several times with water, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and distilled. The residue was dried in oil-pump and dehydrated with anhydrous KHSO_4 (6.3 g.) at 160° . It was worked up as usual and distilled, b. p. $135^\circ/4$ mm., yield 1.1 g.

(b). Ketone (II, 9.5 g.) was also reduced with Na (10.5 g.), water (60 c.c.) and ether (200 c.c.) as usual. The reduction product was treated as above with anhydrous KHSO_4 (20 g.) The unsaturated compound, b.p. $135^\circ/4$ mm. was obtained in 3 g. yield.

The above unsaturated compound (1 g.) was heated with sulphur (0.32 g.) at 230° for 1 hour. The hydrocarbon was sublimed. Yield 200 mg. It was further crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$), m.p. 110° ; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, m.p. 110° , showed no depression (Literature records 112° ; Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 691).

Preparation of Biphenyl Derivatives

(a) *4'-Methoxy-4-methyl-biphenyl*.—*p*-Methylcyclohexanone (15 g.) was added to a cooled solution of the Grignard complex of *p*-bromoanisole prepared from Mg (4.81 g.), *p*-bromoanisole (37.5 g.) and ether (150 c.c.) and kept overnight. Next day it was refluxed for one hour and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and was extracted with ether. After removal of ether the residue was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. $165^\circ\text{--}170^\circ/4$ mm. The liquid rapidly solidified. It was crystallised several times from hot alcohol in which it was soluble, m.p. 72° , yield 12 g. (Found: C, 83.24; H, 9.17. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.16; H, 8.91 per cent).

The above unsaturated compound (2 g.) was heated with sulphur for half an hour at 230° and sublimed at reduced pressure. It was then crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$), m. p. 110° . (Found: C, 84.4; H, 7.49. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.84; H, 7.07 per cent).

(b). *4'-Methoxy-3-methyl-biphenyl* was prepared following the above procedure from *m*-methylcyclohexanone. The unsaturated compound after Grignard reaction

distilled at $150^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, 83.71 ; H, 9.10. $C_{14}H_{18}O$ requires C, 83.16 ; H, 8.91 per cent).

On dehydrogenation the substituted hydrocarbon was obtained which on distillation (b.p. $140^{\circ}/3$ mm.), followed by crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. $60^{\circ}-80^{\circ}$), melted at $49-50^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 84.13 ; H, 7.42. $C_{14}H_{14}O$ requires C, 84.84 ; H, 7.07 per cent).

(c) *4'-Methoxy-2-methyl-biphenyl* was also prepared in the same manner starting from *o*-methylcyclohexanone. The unsaturated compound boiled at $145^{\circ}-147^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, 82.40 ; H, 9.09. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.16 ; H, 8.91 per cent) On dehydrogenation it furnished an oil, b.p. $135^{\circ}-137^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 84.41 ; H, 7.37. $C_{14}H_{14}O$ requires C, 84.84 ; H, 7.07 per cent).

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-6-methylcyclohex-2-ene-1-one (IV)

(a) *Condensation of ω -Chloro-*p*-methoxypropio-phenone with Ethyl ν Methylsodioacetate.*—To the sodio derivative prepared from 2.3 g. of sodium dust, benzene (70 c.c.), ethyl methylacetoacetate (26 g.) and absolute alcohol (8.5 c.c.), ω -chloro-*p*-methoxypropio-phenone (13 g.) (Kennar and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 301) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. The solution was cooled, acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added followed by water ; benzene layer was washed with 5% NaOH solution several times and then with water. The solvent was removed. Crude ester thus obtained was 24 g.

Treatment of it with semicarbazide hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate furnished a solid derivative. It dissolves in excess of boiling alcohol. On cooling small needle-shaped crystals separated out, m.p. $201-202^{\circ}$.

(b) *Hydrolysis of the above Substituted Ester.*—The substituted ester (23.5 g.) was hydrolysed with 2.5% KOH solution according to the method of Wilds (*loc. cit.*), worked up as usual and distilled, b.p. $185^{\circ}-187^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 9 g. It rapidly solidified on distillation. It was crystallised several times from petroleum ether (b.p. $60^{\circ}-80^{\circ}$), m.p. 76° . (Found : C, 77.83 ; H, 7.87. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 77.77 ; H, 7.40 per cent).

The *oxime* of the unsaturated ketone was prepared by the alcohol-pyridine method, and crystallised as rhombic crystals from petroleum ether (b. p. $60^{\circ}-80^{\circ}$), m. p. $163-64^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 73.25 ; H, 7.45 ; N, 6.13. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 72.7 ; H, 7.40 ; N, 6.06 per cent).

3-(p-Methoxy-phenyl)-6-methylcyclohexanone : Hydrogenation of the Unsaturated Ketone (IV).—The unsaturated ketone (IV, 4.2 g.) was hydrogenated in presence of Adam's catalyst (0.1 g.). Theoretical quantity of hydrogen was absorbed. It was worked up as usual and distilled, b.p. $170^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 3.55 g. This was further fractionated, the fraction boiling at $135^{\circ}-137^{\circ}/1$ mm. was collected. (Found : C, 76.80 ; H, 8.41. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.06, H, 8.25 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared by refluxing the ketone (1 g.) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.2 g.), pyridine (1.5 c.c.), absolute alcohol (4 c.c.) for 8 hours. On

dilution with water the oxime separated out. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol several times, m.p. 173-74°. This showed no depression in melting point when mixed with the oxime of the ketone obtained by the Friedel-Craft reaction.

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter, Palit Professor of Chemistry (Retired), University of Calcutta and Prof. D. K. Banerjee of the College of Engineering and Technology, Bengal, for their kind interest and encouragement and to Dr. P. C. Mukherji and Mr. Jadugopal Dutta, M. Sc. for their valuable co-operation during the progress of these investigations. Thanks are also due to the authorities of this college for kindly granting permission to work in the organic research laboratories, to one of us (H.N.K.)

ORGANIC RESEARCH LABORATORIES,
CHEMICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT,
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY,
JADABPUR, BENGAL

Received February 1 1949